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Facile Fabrication of Large-Area Biofunctionalized Metallic Nanostructures for High Performance Affinity Plasmonic Biosensors

Abstract: We present an approach to the facile preparation of biointerface-capped periodic arrays of gold nanoparticles (Au NP) with controlled plasmonic and advanced sensing properties. It relies on feedback-controlled UV-laser interference lithography combined with a novel ion milling method. These advancements improved preparation reproducibility yielding localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) wavelength tuned to near infrared spectrum with standard deviation of 10 nm. Moreover, a novel molecular toolkit of thiols and silatrane linkers with carboxybetaine / sulfobetaine headgroups is employed for orthogonal chemical modification of Au NPs and passivation of the optically non-active sensor chip regions, to prevent non-specific sorption of molecules from liquid samples. As part of this toolbox, we report the use of mercaptopropyl silatrane as an adhesion-promoting coating for attaching Au NPs to an oxide substrate, replacing the traditionally used strongly absorbing chromium. The developed biofunctional optical nanostructures show LSPR with improved quality factor and enable 2.5-fold increase in accuracy for tracking of biomolecular binding on their surface via LSPR wavelength variations monitoring. In addition, we demonstrated a strategy to mitigate unspecific

biomolecule sorption not only at the plasmonic hotspot on the metal surface, but also on the often-overlooked oxide substrate, highlighting the importance of the described orthogonal modification.

Keywords: metallic nanostructures, plasmonic sensor, silatrane monolayer, adhesion layer, electron cyclotron wave resonance

1 Introduction

Metallic nanostructures become routinely used building blocks in numerous fields including optical sensing and biosensing [1], optical spectroscopy [2], counterfeit protection [3], integrated optics [4], and catalysis [5] to mention several important examples. Such nanomaterials provide unique optical properties that are attributed to the excitation of surface plasmons originating from resonant collective oscillations of charge density and associated electromagnetic field. These optical resonances are accompanied with tight confinement of the electromagnetic field in vicinity to the metallic nanostructures, which leads to strongly increased field intensity and local density of optical states. Such characteristics allow for the realization of a wide range of functionalities including the development of extremely small optically driven heat sources [6] employed in micro and nanomachines [7], amplification of weak fluorescence [8],[9], Raman scattering [10] or infrared absorption [11] signals serving in detection of and bioimaging applications, as well as the utilization of direct label-free probing of affinity captured analytes from binding-induced minute refractive index changes [12] or colorimetric changes [13].

All these applications demand design and specific tailoring of metallic nanostructure, which has been reflected by the development of numerous types of preparation routes. Chemical synthesis provides a rapidly improving preparation means offering highly monodisperse colloid materials with well-controlled size and shape [14]. Metallic nanoparticle colloids can be used for self-assembly to ordered 2D [15] or 3D [16] crystal structures and they are also increasingly popular for the preparation of plasmonic nanoantennas in conjunction with DNA origami scaffolds [17]. On solid substrates, electron beam [18] and focused ion beam [19] lithography represent established tools that provide almost ultimate precision and control over 2D shape. However, these methods provide only limited throughput and rely on complex vacuum instrumentation suitable for structuring of narrow footprint at micron scale. Therefore, other approaches have been pursued for more practical and potentially scaled up preparation of metallic nanostructures, with the prominent example being UV-nanoimprint lithography (UV-NIL) [20]. By using a master topography structure that is transferred to a working stamp, repeating copying process over cm^2 or larger areas allows for precise preparation of numerous types of corrugated metallic surfaces as well as metallic nanoparticle structures with the additional lift-off process [21]. Similarly, UV-laser interference lithography (UV-LIL) is a method that allows for facile large area structuring by periodically corrugated metallic surfaces as well as for the preparation of 2D periodic arrays of nanoparticles in conjunction with lift-off [22] or dry etching [23] steps. An overview of available methods is presented in Table S1 in supporting information. With respect to UV-NIL, UV-LIL offers means for facile adapting of the preparation process by on-demand tuning of the fabricated metallic nanostructure pattern (period, feature size, etc.) without the need of additional fabrication of a master structure.

In bioanalytical sensor applications, plasmonic nanostructures are often used for probing of biomolecules present in complex biological fluids comprising abundant amounts of other non-target species. In order to prevent masking of the response due to the target analyte and to avoid blocking of the surface of metallic nanostructures by other molecules, their surface is often chemically modified to repel fouling [24]. Moreover, the surface of metallic nanostructures serving in affinity-based biosensors is modified with chemical units enabling anchoring of additional biofunctional molecules for specific capture of the target species from the analyzed liquid sample [25]. Up to now, a great variety of molecular architectures was used for the modification of metals and besides most common thiol self-assembled monolayers (SAM) with hydroxyl or oligoethylene glycol headgroups [26], also polymer brushes [27] and polymer networks [28] were pursued with these hydrophilic moieties. These systems were designed to function as unspecific sorption-resistant biointerfaces suitable for the immobilization of ligands such as antibodies [29], lower molecular weight nanobodies [30], or aptamers [31]. In the field of plasmonic biosensors,

currently most efficient biofunctional coatings were reported based on incorporating of zwitterionic moieties in similar formats of thiol SAMs [32], polymer brushes [33] as well as polymer networks [34].

Herein, we report on a facile route to biofunctionalized periodic arrays of metallic nanostructures that can be prepared over large cm^2 areas with high reproducibility. It is based on diffraction measurement-based feedback-controlled UV-laser interference lithography with a new version of electron cyclotron wave resonance (ECWR) dry etching. It takes advantage of a molecular toolkit consisting of silatrane- and thiol-based molecules bearing zwitterionic sulfobetaine and carboxybetaine headgroups. These moieties provide excellent antifouling properties on both metal and glass surfaces while enabling the covalent coupling of ligands within the confined field of localized surface plasmons. The yielded plasmonic structure benefits from improved quality factor of LSPR owing to attachment of Au NP to the glass surface by an optically non-absorbing mercapto-silatrane linker layer. With respect to regularly used chromium-based adhesion promoting layers, the sharper LSPR allows tracking of molecular binding-induced refractive index changes with improved accuracy due to decreased optical damping. Moreover, the controlled functionalization of metallic nanostructure combined with the passivation of underneath glass substrate (which is also probed by the confined surface plasmon field and often overlooked in plasmonic biosensor design) helps mitigate false responses associated with unspecific sorption.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

S1805 G2 positive photoresist and AZ 303 developer were purchased from Micro Resist Technology (Germany). Propylene glycol monomethyl ether acetate was obtained from Merck (Germany). Phosphate buffer saline tablets (PBS: 137 mM NaCl, 10 mM phosphate, 2.7 mM KCl, pH=7.4), bovine serum albumin (BSA), Tween-20, and HellmanexTM III solution were obtained from Sigma (Germany). PBS-Tween-BSA was prepared by adding Tween20 (0.05%) and BSA (0.1% or 0.5%) to PBS solution. N-(3-Dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC hydrochloride) and N-Hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) were purchased from Merck (Germany). Ethanol (96%), ethanol absolute ($\geq 99.8\%$) and sucrose (analytical grade) were obtained from Penta (Czech Republic). Ethanolamine (1M pH 8.5) was acquired from Cytiva (USA). All buffer solutions were prepared by using ultrapure water (Direct-Q 3UV, Merck, Germany).

2.2 Biomaterials

Recombinant chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4 (CSPG4) protein was expressed and purified according to a previously reported process [35] and murine antibodies against CSPG4 (Ep3) were prepared according to a previously reported procedure [36]. Nanobodies 2LP-28 specific against CSPG4 were identified from a combinatorial VHH Phage Display Library with an estimated size of 1.0×10^9 , exhibiting an effective insert ratio of 97.2%. Following three rounds of solid/liquid phase panning, enrichment was confirmed by output/input ratio and phage pool ELISA. Sequencing of 48 monoclonal clones revealed 34 unique sequences, all of which were expressed using a high-throughput mammalian cell system. Binding ELISA demonstrated that 29 of 34 nanobodies bound to human CSPG4, while SPR analysis confirmed affinity in 27 of 34 clones. Nanobody 2LP-28 was selected for its high association and low dissociation rates to CSPG4, making it a promising candidate for further development.

2.3 Synthesis of biointerface toolkit

Mercaptopropylsilatrane (MP-SiT), zwitterionic carboxybetaine and sulfobetaine thiols (CB-SH and SB-SH, respectively), and sulfobetaine silatrane (SB-SiT) were synthesized as documented in previous reports [37], [38], [39]. Details are reported in the supporting information in section "S2. Synthesis of biointerface toolkit".

2.4 Deposition of thin films

Glass microscope slides ($20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$) were cleaned in a bath of Piranha solution prepared with a ratio $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 : \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ of 3:1 for 45 min and then sequentially sonicated in milliQ water, 1% Hellmanex, milliQ water, and 97% ethanol, for 15 min each. The glass slides were then dried in a stream of nitrogen and treated with oxygen plasma (PDC-32G, from Harrick Plasma, USA) at 18 W for 20 seconds to remove organic contaminations and produce hydroxyl groups on the surface. For the MP-SiT deposition procedure, derived from the report [40], the substrates were immediately immersed in a 5 mM solution of MP-SiT in anhydrous ethanol and placed in an oven at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 h. After the coating, the slides were sonicated in anhydrous ethanol for 15 min to remove excess adsorbed species from the formed monolayer. Finally, the cleaned substrates were dried in a stream of nitrogen and baked in a vacuum oven at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 5 mbar for 2h. The substrates were subsequently coated with a 50 nm thick gold layer by magnetron sputtering. A DC planar magnetron sputtering system with a 50 mm circular target was used for the deposition of chromium and gold thin films. The applied DC power was kept at $P_{\text{DC}}=200 \text{ W}$ and the argon gas pressure was $p_{\text{Ar}} \approx 0.7 \text{ Pa}$. For the purpose of comparison between adhesion layers, a 2 nm thick chromium layer was deposited below the gold thin film with the magnetron sputtering setup. The chromium deposition was done only on half of the substrate by using a movable mask designed. After the chromium deposition, the mask was rotated, leaving the whole area of the substrate exposed to gold deposition. The mask rotation process occurred without breaking the chamber's vacuum.

2.5 UV-laser interference lithography

Microposit S1805 positive resist was spun on the gold surface to form a layer with a thickness of 150-170 nm, obtained by diluting the resist 1:1 with propylene glycol monomethyl ether acetate and using the rotation speed of 4500 rpm for 45 s. The coated substrates were soft-baked at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on a hot plate for 120 s before patterning via UV-LIL. A coherent beam emitted from a HeCd laser (IK 3031 R-C from Kimmon, Japan) at wavelength 325 nm was expanded and split into two collimated beams by using the Lloyd's mirror configuration. The angle of interfering beams was set to $\theta=20^\circ 41'$ yielding a sinusoidally modulated field with a periodicity of $\Lambda=460 \text{ nm}$. The intensity of the beam at the sample holder was measured to be 0.42 mW/cm^2 . The pattern was recorded to the photoresist for 10 seconds in the horizontal and vertical directions with a total exposure dose of 8.4 mJ/cm^2 . The recorded photoresist layer was etched with AZ-303 developer to form periodically corrugated polymer mask on the gold surface by adjusting the development time in the range $t_{\text{dev}}=20\text{-}140 \text{ s}$. In order to monitor the depth of the periodically modulated polymer mask, diffraction efficiency measurement setup was assembled with a probing diode laser (LDM635 from Thorlabs, UK) emitting at $\lambda=635 \text{ nm}$ and a power meter (S120VC from Thorlabs, UKS120VC).

2.6 Dry etching

To transfer the recorded photoresist pattern to the underlying gold film, non-reactive argon ion plasma etching was implemented, using a custom-built RF (13.56 MHz) low pressure electron cyclotron wave resonance (ECWR) plasma source [41], [42] with RF bias applied to the substrate holder. The dry etching system consisted of an RF circular electrode with a DC magnetic field generated by a pair of DC coils placed outside the vacuum reactor chamber. The magnitude of the DC magnetic field could be adjusted in the range of $B=0\text{-}4 \text{ mT}$. The electron cyclotron wave is generated inside the volume of the RF coil, and by control the DC magnetic field, the wavelength of the electron cyclotron wave propagating along the vector of the DC magnetic field can be tuned, and resonant conditions can be achieved [43]. The plasma density increases rapidly upon onset of the wave resonance, $n_{\text{ie}} \approx 10^{17} \text{ m}^{-3}$, allowing the argon gas pressure to be very low, $p_{\text{Ar}} < 0.1 \text{ Pa}$. In this setup, part of the RF power is fed to the substrate holder, which is electrically isolated from ground, via a capacitor. Due to the RF voltage applied to the nonlinear plasma sheath at the substrate surface, a DC bias U_{bias} (measured with respect to ground) is generated on this plasma sheath and it accelerates positive ions to the substrate surface. The total RF power applied to the plasma etching system was $P_{\text{ECWR}}=300 \text{ W}$ and under the conditions presented $U_{\text{bias}} \approx -400 \text{ V}$.

2.7 Morphological characterization

The morphology of the nanoparticle arrays and of the nanopatterned photoresist layer was investigated with atomic force microscopy (Dimension Icon from Bruker, US). The measurements were carried out at room temperature, in ambient environment, in Peak Force Tapping mode with ScanAsyst Air tips (Bruker; $k=0.4$ N/m; nominal tip radius 2 nm). Measured topographies have 512×512 points² resolution and their profiles were analyzed using the free Gwyddion software.

2.8 Numerical simulations

A *MATLAB* script was used to simulate the effects of the development step on an irradiated photoresist layer. The simulation assumes that different regions of the photoresist are etched at varying rates during development, proportionally to the irradiation dose, and that etching occurs always perpendicular to the layer surface (the respective script is available at a repository and can be accessed via the doi number 10.5281/zenodo.14726041).

For the visualization of the LSP field distribution in vicinity to Au NPs on glass surface contacted with water, we simulated the electromagnetic response using a finite element method electromagnetic simulation (*COMSOL Multiphysics*). The geometrical parameters describing arrays of disk-shaped Au NPs were set as diameter $D=160$ nm, height $d_m=50$ nm, and period $A=460$ nm. A BK7 glass was used as substrate and water as superstrate. The refractive index of gold was taken from [44] and the refractive index of water at room temperature and of BK7 were selected from the software library. Periodic boundaries were applied, and perfectly matched layers were used to avoid spurious reflections at the boundaries. The plane-wave light with wavelength $\lambda=750$ nm was polarized as a transverse magnetic (TM), with the main electric field component perpendicular to the axis of the gold disk. Electric field magnitude values were normalized to those of the incident (excitation) plane wave E_0 .

2.9 Preparation of biointerface with thiol / silatrane – based molecular toolkit

Following the preparation of Au NP arrays, mixed thiol monolayer from CB-SH and SB-SH was self-assembled on the surface of Au NPs, according to a protocol reported previously for flat gold surfaces [38]. Subsequently, SB-SiT were immobilized on the glass surface between Au NPs, according to a reported procedure [39]. Briefly, the prepared Au NP arrays were rinsed with ethanol and treated with UV ozone cleaner (from Jelight, USA) for 30 min. Immediately after the process, they were immersed overnight in an ethanol solution with dissolved CB- and SB-thiols at concentration of 0.1 mM and 0.9 mM, respectively, to form a self-assembled monolayer (SAM). After rinsing with ethanol, the SAM-modified substrates were immersed in a 5 mM solution of SB-SiT in anhydrous ethanol and placed in an oven at 60 °C for 6 h. After the coating, the substrates were dried in a stream of nitrogen and baked in a vacuum oven at 80 °C and 5 mbar for 2h.

2.10 Optical sensor configuration

Au NP arrays on a glass substrate were clamped against a flow-cell and loaded in a transmission spectroscopy setup. A transparent quartz glass with inlet and outlet apertures was pressed against the substrate with Au NPs separated by a thin PDMS gasket forming a flow chamber of volume 21 μ L. The gasket was cut with elliptical shape (long axis 11 mm, short axis 6 mm) from a PDMS sheet with a thickness of approx. 0.4 mm using a plotter (Silhouette Cameo 4 from Silhouette America, USA). Liquid samples were delivered to the flow-cell via tubing (Tygon LMT-55 from Ismatek, Germany) by using a peristaltic pump (Reglo Digital Multichannel from Ismatek, Germany) at a flow rate of 30 μ L min⁻¹.

A polychromatic beam emitted from a halogen lamp of an inverted microscope (Diaphot 200 from Nikon, Japan) was launched through the flow-cell and collected by an objective 3.2x/0.1 (Carl Zeiss Jena, Germany) from a focus spot of diameter 20 μ m. The optical microscope was adapted so the transmitted beam was split at a beamsplitter (CCM1-BS013/M from Thorlabs, UK) enabling its imaging to a microscope camera (Dino-Lite AM7025X from DREXX, Czech Republic) for locating the probed area and its coupling to an optical fiber (FG050LGA from Thorlabs, UK) via a fiber collimator

(F810SMA-780 from Thorlabs, UK). The optical fiber - coupled beam was delivered to a spectrometer (FLAME-T from Ocean Optics, USA) and a dedicated software “FunBIMS” developed at Institute of Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences, was used to process the acquired spectra. In the LSPR biosensor measurements, the sensor output was obtained by tracking changes in the resonant wavelength $\delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}$, which was determined by fitting of the dips in the spectra with a polynomial function. For the spectra acquisition, integration time of 14 ms and accumulation of 90 were applied. The acquired LSPR spectra were then normalized to those measured on a surface without the Au NPs.

3 Results and Discussion

Plasmonic nanostructures were prepared by UV-laser interference lithography with implemented feedback control and a novel dry etching approach, providing improved reproducibility. As illustrated in **Fig.1A-C**, the developed preparation route consisted of a recording of a periodic UV light interference pattern into a photoresist layer followed by its etching in order to yield a thin polymer mask atop a thin gold film that is attached to a glass substrate. Then, the polymer mask was transferred to the gold thin film by Ar milling based on ECWR instrument in order to yield periodic arrays of plasmonic gold nanoparticles – Au NPs. Further this procedure is discussed and its performance quantified in terms of reproducibility of the Au NP morphology characteristics as well the plasmonic properties. The prepared plasmonic nanostructures were applied for LSPR-based plasmonic affinity biosensing and there is reported the implementation of a dedicated chemical toolkit for the modification of prepared Au NPs. As **Fig.1.D** shows, it consists of compounds that provide improved adhesion strength of gold to glass substrate (MP-SiT), it provides a coating that efficiently passivates the glass area in between the Au NPs with an antifouling layer (SB-SiT) and also enable modification of the gold surface with a biointerface (SB-SH and CB-SH) enabling docking of biorecognition elements (BRE) for affinity capture of target analyte.

Fig. 1: Schematics of the preparation route of Au NP arrays consisting of A) recording the UV interference field to the photoresist layer (attached to glass substrate [BK7] carrying adhesion promoting layer [AP] and thin gold film [Au] with a thickness d_m) by using a Lloyd's mirror configuration (described in more detail in Fig.S1), B) feedback-controlled development of the resist to reproducibly form polymer mask (described in more detail in Fig.S2), and C) the transfer of the polymer mask to the underneath thin gold film yielding arrays of Au NPs (with diameter D , period A , and height d_m). D) Chemical structure of the key building blocks employed for the orthogonal chemistry-based modification of Au NP arrays.

3.1 Recording and feedback-controlled development of photoresist mask

The UV-LIL employed a sinusoidally modulated interference field at a wavelength of 325 nm with a period of $\Lambda=460$ nm formed by an optical setup with Lloyd's mirror configuration (see Fig.S1). A substrate carrying a gold film with thickness of 50 nm and a photoresist layer with thickness of 150-170 nm on the top was exposed twice to the sinusoidally modulated UV interference field for the recording time t_{rec} and between the recording steps the substrate orientation was rotated by 90° along the axis parallel to its surface.

Afterwards, the resist layer was developed in order to yield a polymer mask with a corrugated topography and the process was adjusted as follows to obtain periodic arrays of separated disk-shaped resist features. The temporal changes in the surface topography of photoresist layer during the development were monitored with the help of measuring diffraction efficiency of the structure. For such characterization there was chosen a wavelength of 635 nm where the photoresist is not sensitive (absorption range of used photoresist S1805 is of 300-500 nm according to the product datasheet). The diffraction efficiency DE was acquired by using -1st order Littrow configuration (see Fig.S2). As **Fig.2A** reveals, increasing development time t_{dev} leads to initial raising of the diffraction efficiency DE_{-1} reaching a maximum at $t_{\text{dev}}=30-40$ s and afterwards it sharply decreases when t_{dev} is further prolonged. The same trend is observed when series of substrates are prepared and the development is performed in one step for defined t_{dev} (indicated as single development) or for individual substrate that is developed in series of 10 s long steps and the curve is plotted against the accumulated time (indicated as consecutive development steps).

Importantly, the DE_{-1} dependency on its decreasing slope allows to relate the morphology of wet etched resists layer with the diffraction efficiency value. AFM micrographs in **Fig.2B** show that at the peak diffraction efficiency of $DE_{-1}=0.11$ ($t_{\text{dev}}=35$ s), the deeply etched profile of the resist corrugation exhibits approximately sinusoidal shape. When prolonging the development step, with consequent slight decrease in the diffraction efficiency to $DE_{-1}=0.08$ ($t_{\text{dev}}=45$ s), the modulation depth of the sinusoidal grating becomes shallower. However, further development leads to a rapid drop in the diffraction efficiency DE_{-1} and when reaching $DE_{-1}=0.002$ ($t_{\text{dev}}=60$ s), the resist layer has opened windows into the flat gold surface. Further below this value, the topography of the photoresist layer exhibits periodic arrays of separated truncated cone-shaped particles, and their diameter D and height are decreasing when further increasing the development time t_{dev} . Let us note that the AFM micrographs in Fig.2B show small deviations in homogeneity of the photoresist nanostructured mask across the measured area, both in terms of unopened and connected layer and in the spatially separated nanoparticles. These inhomogeneities can be attributed to multiple fabrication factors, particularly to possible deviations in thickness of photoresist layer and nonuniformity of the UV beam intensity used for photoresist exposure. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that for short development time t_{dev} the changes in shape of spatially separated nanoparticles shown in the bottom panels (nanoholes, diamond shaped features) is characteristic of the UV-LIL patterning and it can be exploited for the fabrication of wider range of nanostructure geometries [24].

The character of observed changes in resist layer topography was compared to a model, where the etching process was assumed to proceed perpendicular to the photoresist surface with a rate linearly proportional to the recorded intensity of the UV wavelength of 325 nm (details of the model are available in the "Materials and methods" section). This model allowed for excellent reproduction of the measured topography cross-sections as illustrated in **Fig.2C** and it suggests that for the development times associated with the diffraction efficiency DE_{-1} below 0.002, the photoresist yields a mask of spatially separated nanoparticles with controllable ratio of D/Λ .

Fig. 2: A) Measured dependence of -1st diffraction order efficiency of the photoresist polymer mask on the development time t_{dev} , B) examples of topography of photoresist masks measured with AFM for indicated development time t_{dev} (measured for the single development approach) and C) comparison of acquired cross-sections of the height topography as measured by AFM (see lines in B) with a model.

3.2 ECWR dry etching step

In the subsequent step, the prepared photoresist mask was transferred to the underneath thin gold film through a dry etching process based on a bombardment with argon ions. This step completely removed the gold film from the glass substrate in regions not covered by the photoresist. As the etching rate of the photoresist was lower than the one of gold, the etching time t_{etch} could be adjusted so that the photoresist mask topography was transferred to the gold layer with high accuracy, ensuring sufficiently sharp feature edges. The process was carried out by electron cyclotron wave resonance (ECWR) plasma with a tailored configuration, shown in **Fig.3A**, and the system allowed to homogeneously structure an area of about 16 cm². It is important to note that due to the low pressure in the plasma $p_{Ar} \approx 0.1$ Pa, the total heating flux on the substrate was quite low compared to typical values obtained in classical RF capacitive non-reactive ion etching, which is usually performed at higher pressure $p_{Ar} \approx 1$ Pa [45]. The ECWR RF plasma used has similar characteristics to the classical RF inductively coupled plasma (RF-ICP) operating at similar low pressure range $p_{Ar} \approx 0.1-0.2$ Pa, but due to the electron cyclotron wave resonance effect, the plasma density is higher, and the plasma is more uniform [43]. Furthermore, due to the very low pressure of the argon gas and the high plasma density, the ion flux on the substrate was large, allowing to effectively remove the gold material while maintaining the plasma's total heating flux below the substrate's thermal damage threshold.

The etching time t_{etch} was adjusted to 32-38 sec, and an example of the topography of photoresist mask and the respective structure etched into the gold layer is shown in **Fig.3B** and **Fig.3C**. The presented example illustrates that the diameter of prepared Au NPs of $D=197$ nm is close to that of the photoresist mask with $D=181$ nm (the diameter was defined from a cut in the plane parallel to the substrate surface at the half height of the feature's maximum). After dry etching, any residues of the photoresist mask are removed from the surface by rinsing thoroughly with acetone, and the Au NPs exhibit flat top, with height approximately $d_m=55-60$ nm which is slightly above the thickness of the deposited Au film due to the effect of weak etching into the glass substrate.

The sample-to-sample reproducibility was tested in terms of diameter variations of Au NP arrays. For this purpose, a set of 10 samples was prepared and examined by AFM as can be seen in supporting information (see Fig.S3 and Fig.S4). These samples were prepared with the diffraction efficiency feedback set to $DE_{-1}=0.001-0.002$ (corresponding to photoresist mask nanoparticles with measured diameter

$D=168\pm 8$ nm) and the obtained diameter for the gold nanoparticles was of $D=190\pm 16$ nm (error corresponds to standard deviation).

Fig. 3: A) Schematics of the vacuum apparatus for ECWR-based dry etching of Au NP arrays with B) examples of the AFM topography before and after the dry etching step, C) Cross-section of AFM topography on an individual Au NP before and after etching step.

3.3 LSPR - effect of adhesion promoting layer and reproducibility

The reproducibility and quality of LSPR spectra were examined in terms of quality factor Q , which is often used to capture damping in resonant optical oscillators and serves for benchmarking of numerous plasmonic nanostructures. It can be described as a ratio of the resonance wavelength and width $Q=\lambda_{LSPR}/\Delta\lambda_{LSPR}$ and for the examined Au NP structures its value was determined from the measured transmission spectra. As can be seen in **Fig.4A** and **Fig.4B**, the LSPR exhibits itself as a dip in transmission spectra with additional sharp spectral features that can be attributed to the occurrence of Rayleigh anomalies associated with falling of diffraction orders behind horizon in glass substrate ($\lambda_{R-Glass}$) or the superstrate (λ_{R-Air}).

Fig.4A shows that both λ_{LSPR} and $\Delta\lambda_{LSPR}$ are affected when the traditionally used chromium adhesion promoting layer (AP, see Fig.1) is replaced by the MP-SiT. With respect to the spectra acquired for a sample with chromium layer, its substitution with MP-SiT film (Au NP arrays with chromium and MP-SiT adhesion promoting layer were prepared side-by-side on individual substrates) leads to a blue shift of λ_{LSPR} wavelength and it is accompanied by substantial narrowing of the resonance described by $\Delta\lambda_{LSPR}$. The shift in λ_{LSPR} can be in part explained by a decrease of the effective refractive index of the nanoparticles that affects the LSP resonance condition. In addition, in presence of the chromium adhesion layer, the LSP resonance condition also changes with the LSP dephasing time caused by the chromium-increased Ohmic losses, leading to both the shifting in λ_{LSPR} and the broadening of $\Delta\lambda_{LSPR}$, as investigated by prior works for similar plasmonic systems [46, 47]. For the tested geometries with the period of $A=460$ nm, these changes lead to the improvement of respective quality factor Q by an average of ~50% [20% i), 40% ii), and 80% iii)]. The obtained values as low as $Q=6.8$ for iii) were obtained for the LSPR wavelength of $\lambda_{LSPR}=740$ nm and width $\Delta\lambda_{LSPR}=108$ nm, determined as full width in the half minimum. Such Q factor is comparable to the values of other reported single nanoparticles ($Q\sim 5$) [48], [49] single nanorods ($Q\sim 7$) [50] or nanoparticle dimers ($Q\sim 10$) [51], [52].

In order to assess information on the reproducibility, LSPR spectra were measured for a set of 10 samples carrying Au NP arrays that were already characterized with AFM in terms of morphology in the previous section. As **Fig.4B** documents, all structures were prepared with MP-SiT and they exhibited LSPR wavelength of $\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}=742\pm 10$ nm and LSPR dip width of $\Delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}=90\pm 10$ nm when contacted with air, for an average Q factor of 8.3 ± 0.8 . The error in these parameters was calculated as standard deviation. An apparent deviation in transmission spectrum can be observed for sample 3 that exhibited substantially lower Q factor of 6.7. The occurrence of this irregular spectrum can be attributed to the fact that the sample was etched for a total of 32 seconds, but the process was carried out in two separate steps (25 seconds + 7 seconds). The repeated ignition of the sputtering resulted in a less effective process overall, allowing for a few residual nanometers of gold film in between the Au NPs (as indicated by AFM measurement). This explains the overall lower transmission values for the wavelengths outside of the plasmonic resonance bandwidth, because of partial reflection. Furthermore, the presence of a thin gold film between Au NPs doesn't allow for strong confinement of light at their edges, resulting in increased losses and decreased extinction efficiency.

Fig. 4: A) Examples of transmission spectra with the LSPR on three Au NP arrays attached to the glass substrate via MP-SiT and Cr adhesion promoting layer [the diameter of Au NP was varied in the shown examples and curves i) are offset by 0, ii) by 50 and iii) by 100%]. The transmission spectra were measured for Au NP arrays in contact with air. B) Illustration of reproducibility showing the LSPR spectra from a batch of 10 samples processed with feedback-controlled t_{dev} , MP-SiT adhesion-promoting layer, and dry etching time $t_{\text{etch}}=32\text{-}38$ sec. Transmission spectra measured for a substrate in contact with air.

3.4 LSPR refractometric sensor

The impact of improving the quality factor Q of prepared Au NP arrays by MP-SiT adhesion promoting layer was tested in refractometric sensor experiment based on wavelength interrogation of LSPR. In order to do so, Au NP arrays with chromium and MP-SiT adhesion promoting layer were prepared side-by-side on individual substrates. These substrates were contacted with a flow-cell and loaded to a transmission spectroscopy setup described in **Fig.5A**. A translation stage allowed precise positioning of the probing optical beam across the sample surface, aided by a camera imaging the probing spot at the Au NP arrays surface. Liquid aqueous samples spiked with sucrose in varying concentrations (2%, 4%, 6%, and 8% in ultrapure water), exhibiting refractive index between $n_b=1.333$ and 1.345, were sequentially flowed over the substrate surface of Au NPs and the beam position was cycled between the areas with chromium and the ones with MP-SiT adhesion-promoting layers. Refractive index – induced variations in the LSPR transmission spectra were measured and induced changes in LSPR wavelength λ_{LSPR} were tracked and plotted against time. **Fig.5B** shows transmission spectra near the LSPR wavelengths for the

Au NP array with MP-SiT (red curves) and chromium (green curves) and **Fig.5C** presents the sensorgrams for real-time tracking of λ_{LSPR} obtained by fitting the minimum of LSPR transmission spectrum dip.

Fig. 5: A) schematics of the optical sensor system for wavelength interrogation of LSPR by using transmission spectra, B) comparison of LSPR spectra shift due to the refractive index change of water-based sucrose solutions in contact with the Au NP arrays, and C) respective changes in the sensorgram kinetics with real-time tracking of λ_{LSPR} .

The tracking of LSPR wavelength in **Fig.5C** reveals the effects of different adhesion layers on the noise characteristics and sensitivity of the sensor. The inset shows a baseline on both Au NP arrays and respective noise σ was quantified with the standard deviation. For the resonance of MP-SiT-attached Au NP arrays, it yielded $\sigma=0.02$ nm and for the Cr-attached plasmonic nanostructures $\sigma=0.04$ nm. Regarding sensitivity S , defined as a ratio of sensor output $\Delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}$ and refractive index change Δn_b , the MP-SiT-bound sensor surface showed approximately $S=235$ nm/RIU compared to approximately 187 nm/RIU for the Cr-bound Au NPs. Consequently, the refractive index resolution defined as σ/S was evaluated approximately 8.5×10^{-5} RIU for the MP-SiT adhesion layer and 2.1×10^{-4} RIU for the chromium adhesion layer, resulting in a 2.5-fold improvement for the MP-SiT-attached Au NP. As the Au NP dimensions are consistent by fabrication across the two regions, the observed differences in optical response can be only attributed to the different adhesion layers.

3.5 LSPR biosensor with orthogonal biointerface architecture

The developed substrates with Au NP arrays were tested to serve as sensor chips in LSPR-based observation of specific interaction between a protein molecule attached to the sensor surface and its affinity partner present in a liquid sample. The novel thiol/silatrane molecular toolkit was used for selective modification of Au NPs with biofunctional biointerface and for the passivation of the oxide surface with antifouling motifs. As indicated in **Fig.6A**, a mixed thiol monolayer was firstly self-assembled on the surface of Au NPs from caboxybetaine and sulfobetaine thiols (CB-SH and SB-SH dissolved at a molar ratio of 1:9 in the solution reacted with the surface). These molecules exhibit zwitterionic character and the formed SAM combines the properties of CB-SH that is suitable for the immobilization of biorecognition elements via amine coupling and those of SB-SH featuring fouling resistance, superhydrophilicity, and high packing density. Afterwards, the glass area of sensor surface between Au NPs was reacted with sulfobetaine-silatrane (SB-SiT).

The passivation of the oxide (glass) portion of the nanostructure is crucial, as glass represents the majority (about 80%) of the surface area of the sensor chip. When not passivated, unspecific adsorption of species on the oxide surface may lead to depletion of the concentration of target molecules present in the analyzed liquid sample. In addition, unspecific sorption on the oxide can generate false LSPR signal as resonantly excited LSPs probe not only metal surface, but also substantial part the dielectric substrate area to which the Au NPs are attached. Simulations of near field distribution of electromagnetic field presented in **Fig.6B** show its confinement primarily at the gold disk nanoparticle walls with area of

$3.1 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}^2$, and additionally also at a belt surrounding the Au NP base occupied by glass, with an area of $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}^2$ that we defined by using the LSP probing depth of 10 nm. The effect of unspecific sorption to the oxide surface was experimentally investigated on Au NPs that were modified with anti-fouling SB/CB-SH SAM and the LSPR wavelength changes were measured when a solution with 0.5% bovine serum albumin (BSA) was flowed through the biosensor for 15 min, followed by rinsing with a working buffer. Data presented in **Fig.6C** compare measured λ_{LSPR} kinetics on Au NPs with and without the SB-SiT passivation. Both curves show an abrupt increase in the sensor signal upon injecting the solution with BSA and a decrease during the washing of the surface with the working buffer, which can be attributed to the bulk refractive index change Δn_b of the solution. However, after the washing step for the SB-SiT-passivated surface, the sensor response returns to its original baseline, whereas for the structure without SB-SiT passivation, irreversible shift by about 0.2 nm occurs. This can be ascribed to non-specific sorption of BSA molecules onto the oxide surface surrounding the base of the Au NPs. Such non-specific interactions introduce changes that could complicate the interpretation of LSPR biosensor data, expected to probe only the metal surface while excluding the surrounding glass.

The functionality of mixed thiol SAM composed of SB-SH and CB-SH was tested for a chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4 (CSPG4) immunoassay. As **Fig.6D** shows, the Au NP arrays were first functionalized with a nanobody (2LP-28) specific to this analyte by the use of amine coupling. The carboxyl groups of CB-SH were activated by incubation with EDC/NHS in order to covalently couple the nanobody 2LP-28 via its lysine groups. This ligand exhibits low molecular weight of 14 kDa, which is advantageous in LSPR-based biosensors as it occupies minimal space within the probing field, thereby maximizing the available volume of the confined LSP field for affinity capture of the target analyte. PBS solution with 2LP-28 dissolved at a concentration of 200 nM was flowed over the Au NP surface for 30 min followed by 20 min passivation with underacted active ester moieties with ethanolamine. The change in LSPR wavelength baseline of $\delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}=0.7$ nm indicates successful immobilization of the ligand at the plasmonic hotspot probed by the LSP resonance.

In the succeeding part of the experiment, the working buffer was changed to PBS with additional BSA and Tween 20 blockers as seen in **Fig.6E**. For testing the affinity interaction of the nanobody, a control was first performed by flowing 200 nM murine antibody (Ep3) raised against CSPG4. After 20 min incubation on the LSPR biosensor surface, a negligible change in λ_{LSPR} baseline was observed, indicating a minimized physisorption to both Au and SiO_2 part of the nanostructure. Afterwards, the target CSPG4 analyte present at a concentration of 200 nM was reacted with the surface leading to a LSPR wavelength shift of $\delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}=1.3$ nm. This analyte exhibits a large molecular weight of 500 kDa which can explain the increased magnitude of the sensor response when compared to that for immobilization of the nanobody ligand. Importantly, after rinsing, the Ep3 murine antibody was re-incubated on the sensor surface and in this step affinity binding to CSPG4 was observed, confirming the specificity of the interaction on the prepared Au NP nanostructure with SB-SH, CB-SH, and SB-SiT - based biointerface. The change of LSPR wavelength of $\delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}=0.25$ nm was smaller than for CSPG4 due to the lower molecular weight of this immunoglobulin G molecule of 160 kDa.

Fig. 6: A) Chemical structure of the key building blocks employed for the orthogonal chemistry-based modification of Au NP arrays and their functionalization. B) Cross-section of near-field distribution of LSP electromagnetic field supported by a disk gold nanoparticle simulated by finite element method. Logarithmic scale is used in order to visualize the localization of LSP field probing in the surrounding medium. Values larger than zero correspond to electromagnetic field amplitudes above that of the incident wave E_0 . C) LSPR wavelength changes $\delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}$ given by physisorption of BSA, measured on a substrate carrying arrays of Au NPs with and without SB-SiT passivation of the glass surface. D) Sensorgrams with LSPR wavelength changes $\delta\lambda_{\text{LSPR}}$ measured for the functionalization with nanobody 2LP-28 and E) affinity interaction with target CSPG4 protein analyte and antibody Ep3.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we developed a facile route for the preparation of large-area periodic arrays of gold nanoparticles with tailored biointerface that exhibit improved plasmonic performance and enhanced biosensing capabilities. By replacing the traditionally used chromium adhesion layer with a molecular linker based on mercaptopropyl silatrane, we achieved an average of 50% increase in the quality factor of the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) dip. This enhancement translated to a 2.5-fold improvement in refractive index resolution that is ascribed to a reduced noise level of the sensor baseline and an increased sensitivity to refractive index changes. The fabrication process, based on UV-laser interference lithography and a novel dry etching technique, was further refined through the integration of diffraction measurement for feedback-control on the prepared polymer mask. These advancements helped yielding highly reproducible Au NP arrays with chip-to-chip standard deviation of 15 nm in nanoparticle diameters, enabling the tuning of LSPR wavelengths in the near-infrared region with a standard deviation of 10 nm. The employed dry etching system enabled accurate transfer of the polymer mask to the thin metal film at temperatures below the substrate's thermal damage threshold, which otherwise complicates the biointerface preparation. Importantly, the finely tailored plasmonic substrates were chemically modified with a novel molecular toolkit consisting of thiols and silatrane linkers with carboxybetaine and sulfobetaine headgroups. This enabled the selective functionalization of the Au NP surfaces and the passivation of the optically inactive glass substrate. This approach effectively suppressed non-specific molecular sorption in the detection area probed in a plasmonic hotspot – which includes not only the metallic nanostructure but also the often-overlooked glass substrate – offering a route to address this critical factor in biomolecular affinity sensing applications.

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Author contribution: all authors accepted the responsibility for the content of the manuscript and consented to its submission, reviewed all the results, and approved the final version of the manuscript. DCM carried out the preparation of the nanostructures, implemented their modification, arranged the optical sensor measurement and contributed to writing the manuscript. DCM and ABP optimized the silatranes coating protocol. DCM and PA assembled and calibrated the diffraction efficiency measurement setup. GA and DCM prepared and performed the affinity interaction measurement. VTV and CJH synthesized and provided the compounds of the molecular toolkit. EG and ER provided the Human CSPG4 protein and the murine antibodies against CSPG4. JP and KÖ provided the nanobodies 2LP-28 against CSPG4. LF carried out the atomic force microscopy measurements. ZH set up and operated the ECWR-based dry etching instrument and acquired funding. JD conceptualized and supervised the work, acquired funding, and contributed to writing the manuscript.

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Abbreviations

Au NP	Gold nanoparticle
LSPR	Localized surface plasmon resonance
LSP	Localized surface plasmon
UV-LIL	UV laser interference lithography
SAM	Self-assembled monolayer
ECWR	Electron cyclotron wave resonance
ICP	Inductively coupled plasma
BRE	Bio-recognition element
MP-SiT	Mercaptopropyl silatranes
CB-SH	Carboxybetaine thiols
SB-SH	Sulfobetaine thiols
SB-SiT	Sulfobetaine silatranes
CSPG4	Chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4

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